

Studies on MoS₂ Nanoflower by Hydrothermal Route

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Abstract

Synthesis and characterization of MoS₂ nanoflower by using conventional hydrothermal route. The reaction is carried out at 160°C for 12 hours by taking 1:2 proportion of citric acid and ammonium molybdate by adding 2.36 gm of thioacetamide. The obtained powder is characterized by using X-ray Diffractogram and Scanning Electron Microscopy. X-ray Diffractogram reveals that MoS₂ shows hexagonal crystal structure. Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy shows nanoflower type structure. Chemical analysis using Energy Dispersive Spectra (EDS) indicates the presence of Mo & S.

Keywords: Hydrothermal route, Nanoflower, MoS₂.

Introduction

Now days the two dimensional (2-D) and three dimensional (3-D) nanostructured materials have attracted great attention because of their potential applications in functional materials and nano device [1]. The transition metal sulfides, MoS₂ have been studied in research for applications such as lithium batteries, wear resistance and catalytic hybrid sulfurization of petrol [1-2]. Recent research has suggested that MoS₂ crystal can be used in lubrication properties [1]. MoS₂ is a transition metal sulfide with a layered structure where Mo layer is between two sulfur layers which are connected by weak van der Waals forces [3]. Various synthesis methods such as Sol gel, Co-precipitation, Spray Pyrolysis and Chemical vapour deposition [1, 4-7]. Hydrothermal synthesis is widely used because of a simple, low temperature, low cost and high purity [1, 3]. In this work, we report a simple hydrothermal synthesis and characterization of MoS₂ nanoflowers.

Methodology

Material:

Ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, thioacetamide $(\text{CH}_3\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2)$ and citric acid monohydrate $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7)\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All starting materials were high purity AR grade.

Synthesis of MoS_2

MoS_2 nano flower were synthesized by using Ammonium Molybdate tetrahydrate, citric acid and Thioacetamide as a starting material. Citric acid was added to deionized water and Ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate with molar ratio 1:2, stirred at 120°C for 20 min on magnetic stirrer. Then thioacetamide dissolved in deionized water and slowly added to solution

Fig.1 Schematic of MoS_2 Synthesized by Hydrothermal route

mixture. At the end solution brownish black precipitate was transferred in teflon lined stainless steel autoclave and autoclave kept in preheated muffle furnace 160°C for 12 hour. Autoclave cooled at room temperature and obtained product was washed 3 times with ethanol and DI water then filtered. The obtained powder was dry under the IR lamp for 8 hrs.

Material Characterization:

Powder X-ray diffractogram (XRD) was recorded on (Bruker AXS Model: D8 Advances, Germany) using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiations. The micro structural characterization with EDS was studied by using field emission Scanning electron microscopy JEOL. The FTIR spectrum was collected using FT/IR-4700 type A.

Fig.2: X-ray Diffractogram of MoS_2 hydrothermal synthesized powder

Fig.3 a) Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy of MoS_2

Fig.3 b) Energy Dispersive Spectra of MoS_2

Fig. 5 Raman Spectra of MoS₂

Result and Discussion

The synthesized sample was characterized by using x-ray diffractogram (XRD) to study the crystal structure. From the X-ray diffractogram sample shows hexagonal (P63/mmc space group) crystal structure with $a=3.1600 \text{ \AA}$, $c= 12.2900 \text{ \AA}$. No any impurity peaks were found.

Fig.3 a) shows Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) image of synthesized powder of MoS₂. FESEM image show that the MoS₂ nanoflower type structure. The image is nanoflowers agglomeration type structure. Chemical analysis using Energy Dispersive Spectra (EDS) indicates the presence of Mo & S and no any other element excited. Fig. 3 b) shows the EDS pattern of MoS₂ sample.

Fig. 4 FTIR spectrum of hydrothermally synthesized MoS₂ shown in fig.4 There are broad absorption bands at 483 cm⁻¹, 639 cm⁻¹, 839 cm⁻¹, 1037.52 cm⁻¹, 1400.07 cm⁻¹, 1622 cm⁻¹ for prepared sample. The band at 483 cm⁻¹ ascribed to Mo-S bond and at 903 cm⁻¹ is due to S-S bond, 1400.07 cm⁻¹, 1622 cm⁻¹ is due to MoS₂, and broad band between 2600 cm⁻¹ to 3500 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the O-H stretching from intermolecular and intramolecular hydrogen bonds [8].

The Raman spectrum of MoS₂ shown in figure 5. There are two prominent peaks at 381 cm⁻¹ and 397 cm⁻¹ [9].

Conclusion

MoS₂ nanoflowers have been synthesized successfully synthesis of simple hydrothermal route using ammonium molybdate & thioacetamide. X-ray Diffractogram reveals that MoS₂ shows hexagonal crystal structure. Mo and S elements confirmed by EDX spectrum. Raman spectrum MoS₂ shows two peaks at 381 cm⁻¹ and 397 cm⁻¹

Conflicts of interest: The authors stated that no conflicts of interest.

References

1. G. Nagaraju C. N. Tharamani G. T. Chandrappa J. Livage, *Nanoscale Res Lett* (2007) 2:461–468.
2. S. V. Prabhakar Vattikuti and Chan Byon *Journal of Nanomaterials* (2015), 710462, 11.
3. Fangping Wang, Guifang Li, Jinfeng Zheng, Jing Ma, Caixia Yang, Qizhao Wang, *RSC Adv.*, 2018, 8, 3894.
4. M.M. Mdleleni, T. Hyeon, K.S. Suslick, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 120, 6189 (1998)
5. Q. Li, J.T. Newberg, E.C. Walter, J.C. Hemminger, R.M. Penner, *Nano Lett.* 4, 277 (2004)
6. P.R. Bonneau, R.F. Jarvis Jr., R.B. Kaner, *Nature* 349, 510 (1991)

8. M.R. Close, J.L. Petersen, E.L. Kugler, *Inorg. Chem.* 38, 1535 (1999)
9. Sung Kon Kim, Jeong Jae Wie, Qasim Mahmood, Ho Seok Park, *Nanoscale*, (2014) 13.
10. K. C. Lalithambika, K. Shanmugapriya, S. Sriram, *Applied Physics A* (2019) 125:817.

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